

Services and Security in ITS

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Abstract Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) aims to provide innovative services relating to different modes of transport and traffic management and enable various users to be better informed and make safer, more coordinated, and 'smarter' use of transport networks. Considering ITS applications that require information to be relayed multiple hops between cars, vehicular networks are poised to become the most widely distributed and largest scale ad hoc networks. Such challenges and opportunities serve as the background of the widespread interest in vehicular networking by governmental, industrial, and academic bodies. This paper tackles the great variety of Intelligent Transport System applications, its different used cases and security issues. The objective of this tutorial is to integrate and synthesize some areas and applications, technologies discuss with all prospects.

Key words: Intelligent transportation system Transportation Technologies Applications Transport management.

1 Introduction

Vehicular networks are a cornerstone of the envisioned Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS). By enabling vehicles to communicate with each other as well as with roadside base stations, vehicular networks will contribute to safer and more efficient roads by providing timely information to drivers and concerned authorities. Vehicular networking is one of those important uprising technologies that will help us to implement a bunch of applications related to vehicles, vehicle traffic, drivers, passengers and pedestrians.

ITS comprise the vehicles, roadside units and a network infrastructure, as shown in Figure 1. We can say that the purpose of ITS is to take advantage of the appropriate technologies to create "more intelligent" roads, vehicles

and users. EN 302 665 [1] describes an ITS station architecture based upon 4 processing layers identified as access layer, networking & transport layer, facilities layer; and applications layer. r

Fig. 1 ITS entities.

ITS aims to streamline the operation of vehicles, manage vehicle traffic, assist drivers with safety and other information, along with provisioning of convenience applications for passengers. Some of the examples include automated toll collection systems, driver assist systems and other information provisioning systems. The excitement surrounding vehicular networking is not only due to the applications or their potential benefits but also due to the challenges and scale of the solutions. Among technical challenges to be overcome, high mobility of vehicles, wide range of relative speeds between nodes, real-time nature of applications, and a multitude of system and application related requirements can be listed. In this work we give an overview of the ITS in a tutorial way. ITS involves a large number of areas and in this paper we focused on those we believe to be the most relevant mainly services and security issues.

2 Applications and Requirements

Talking of the applications and its use case (utilization of an application in a particular situation with a specific purpose), ITS applications can be classified as follows:

- Active road safety applications
- Traffic efficiency and management applications
- Infotainment applications

2.1 Active road safety applications

These applications are primarily employed to decrease the probability of traffic accidents and the loss of life of the occupants of vehicles. A significant percentage of accidents that occur every year in all parts of the world are associated with intersection, head, rear-end and lateral vehicle collisions. Active road safety applications primarily provide information and assistance to drivers to avoid such collisions with other vehicles. This can be accomplished by sharing information between vehicles and road side units which is then used to predict collisions. Such information can represent vehicle position, intersection position, speed and distance heading. Moreover, information exchange between the vehicles and the road side units is used to locate hazardous locations on roads, such as slippery sections or potholes. Some of the examples of such applications are listed below:

- Intersection collision warning: in this use case, the risk of lateral collisions for vehicles that are approaching road intersections is detected by vehicles or road side units. This information is signaled to the approaching vehicles in order to lessen the risk of lateral collisions [2].
- Lane change assistance: the risk of lateral collisions for vehicles that are accomplishing a lane change with blind spot for trucks is reduced.
- Overtaking vehicle warning: aims to prevent collision between vehicles in an overtake situation, where one vehicle, say vehicle1 is willing to overtake a vehicle, say vehicle3, while another vehicle, say vehicle2 is already doing an overtaking maneuver on vehicle3. Collision between vehicle1 and vehicle2 is prevented when vehicle2 informs vehicle1 to stop its overtaking procedure.
- Head on collision warning: the risk of a head on collision is reduced by sending early warnings to vehicles that are traveling in opposite directions. This use case is also denoted as “Do Not Pass Warning”.
- Rear end collision warning: the risk of rear-end collisions for example due to a slow down or road curvature (e.g., curves, hills) is reduced. The driver of a vehicle is informed of a possible risk of rear-end collision in front.
- Co-operative forward collision warning: a risk of forward collision accident is detected through the cooperation between vehicles. Such types of accidents are then avoided by using either cooperation between vehicles or through driver assistance.
- Emergency vehicle warning: an active emergency vehicle, e.g., ambulance, police car, informs other vehicles in its neighborhood to free an emergency corridor. This information can be re-broadcasted in the neighborhood by other vehicles and road side units.
- Pre-crash Sensing/Warning: in this use case, it is considered that a crash is unavoidable and will take place. Vehicles and the available road side units periodically share information to predict collisions. The exchanged information includes detailed position data and vehicle size and it can be

used to enable an optimized usage of vehicle equipment to decrease the effect of a crash. Such equipment can be actuators, air bags, motorized seat belt pre-tensioners and extensible bumpers.

- Cooperative merging assistance: vehicles involved in a junction merging maneuver negotiate and cooperate with each other and with road side units to realize this maneuver and avoid collisions.
- Emergency electronic brake lights: vehicle that has to hard brake informs other vehicles, by using the cooperation of other vehicles and/or road side units, about this situation.
- Wrong way driving warning: a vehicle detecting that it is driving in wrong way, e.g., forbidden heading, signals this situation to other vehicles and road side units.
- Stationary vehicle warning: in this use case, any vehicle that is disabled, due to an accident, breakdown or any other reason, informs other vehicles and road side units about this situation.
- Traffic condition warning: any vehicle that detects some rapid traffic evolution, informs other vehicles and road side units about this situation.
- Signal violation warning: one or more road side units detect a traffic signal violation. This violation information is broadcasted by the road side unit (s) to all vehicles in the neighborhood.
- Collision risk warning: a road side unit detects a risk of collision between two or more vehicles that do not have the capability to communicate. This information is broadcasted by the road side unit towards all vehicles in the neighborhood of this event.
- Hazardous location notification: any vehicle or any road side unit signals to other vehicles about hazardous locations, such as an obstacle on the road, a construction work or slippery road conditions.
- Control loss warning: this use case is described that is intended to enable the driver of a vehicle to generate and broadcast a control-loss event to surrounding vehicles. Upon receiving this information the surrounding vehicles determine the relevance of the event and provide a warning to the drivers, if appropriate.

2.2 Traffic efficiency and management applications

Traffic efficiency and management applications focus on improving the vehicle traffic flow, traffic coordination and traffic assistance and provide updated local information, maps and in general, messages of relevance bounded in space and/or time. Typical groups of this type of applications are discussed below.

- Speed management: such applications aim to assist the driver to manage the speed of his/her vehicle for smooth driving and to avoid unnecessary

stopping. Regulatory/contextual speed limit notification and green light optimal speed advisory are two examples of this type.

- Cooperative navigation: This type of applications is used to increase the traffic efficiency by managing the navigation of vehicles through cooperation among vehicles and through cooperation between vehicles and road side units. Some examples of this type are traffic information and recommended itinerary provisioning, co-operative adaptive cruise control and platooning.

2.3 Infotainment Applications

These applications are of two types:

- Cooperative local services: this type of applications focus on infotainment that can be obtained from locally based services such as point of interest notification, local electronic commerce and media downloading.
- Global Internet services: this focus is on data that can be obtained from global Internet services. Typical examples are Communities services, which include insurance and financial services, fleet management and parking zone management, and ITS station life cycle, which focus on software and data updates [3].

2.4 Requirements

Vehicular networking requirements can be classified into following groups:

- Strategic requirements: These requirements are related to: 1. The level of vehicular network deployment, e.g., minimum penetration threshold 2. Strategies defined by governments and commissions.
- Economical requirements: These requirements are related to economical factors, such as business value once the minimum penetration value is reached; perceived customer value of the use case, purchase cost and on-going cost and time needed for the global return of the invested financial resources.
- System capabilities requirements: These requirements are related to the system capabilities, which are:
 - Radio communication capabilities, such as (1) single hop radio communication range, (2) used radio frequency channels, (3) available bandwidth and bit rate, (4) robustness of the radio communication channel, (5) level of compensation for radio signal propagation difficulties e.g., using road side units.

- Network communication capabilities, such as (1) mode of dissemination: unicast, broadcast, multicast, geocast (broadcast only within a specified area), (2) data aggregation, (3) congestion control, (4) message priority, (5) management means for channel and connectivity realization, (6) support of IPv6 or IPv4 addressing, (7) mobility management associated with changes of point of attachment to the Internet.
 - Vehicle absolute positioning capabilities, such as (1) Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), e.g., Global Positioning System (GPS), (2) Combined positioning capabilities, e.g., combined GNSS with information provided by a local geographical map.
 - Other vehicle capabilities, such as (1) vehicle interfaces for sensors and radars, (2) vehicle navigation capabilities. Vehicle communication security capabilities, such as (1) respect of privacy and anonymity, (2) integrity and confidentiality, (3) resistance to external security attacks, (4) authenticity of received data, (5) data and system integrity.
- System performance requirements: These requirements are related to the system performance, which are: (1) vehicle communication performance, such as maximum latency time, frequency of updating and resending information, (2) vehicle positioning accuracy, (3) system reliability and dependability, such as radio coverage, bit error rate, black zones (zones without coverage). (4) Performance of security operations, such as performance of signing and verifying messages and certificates.
 - Organizational requirements: These requirements are related to organizational activities associated with deployment, which are: (1) common and consistent naming repository and address directory for applications and use cases, (2) IPv6 or IPv4 address allocation schemes, (3) suitable organization to ensure interoperability between different Intelligent Transport Systems, (4) suitable organization to ensure the support of security requirements, (5) suitable organization to ensure the global distribution of global names and addresses in vehicles.
 - Legal requirements: These requirements are related to legal responsibilities, which are: (1) support and respect of customer's privacy, (2) support the liability/responsibility of actors, (3) support the lawful interception.
 - Standardization and certification requirements: These requirements are related to standardization and certification, which are: (1) support of system standardization, (2) support of Intelligent Transport System station standardization, (3) support of product and service conformance testing, (4) support of system interoperability testing, (5) support of system risk management.

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3 Security Challenges in ITS

ITS has been around for quite a few years. Although different standardizing organizations are aiming to develop and deploy the ITS in solving real world scenarios, less attention is being paid to the security challenges and vulnerabilities that are created as a result of these developments. Many researchers have popped up describing different security weaknesses and their possible solutions. The characterization of these vulnerabilities varies from researcher to researcher. This section gathers security challenges and issues as described in existing research proposals. Following are the main challenges in current ITS system.

3.1 Confidentiality

Confidentiality of stored or in-transit information means that it should not be revealed to any third party not involved in communication. The information itself and details of each and every ITS entity should be protected from unnecessary and unauthorized disclosure. Hence any unapproved party should not be able to deduce the location, route or profile of ITS end user from the communication channel traffic [1].

3.2 Integrity

Integrity deals with protection against unnecessary modification or deletion of data at rest or in motion. The data should be secured against such malicious users which manipulate the data during transmission or while being stored [1]. This way accidents due to wrong information transmit can be avoided. The main challenges include unauthorized access to restricted information, loss of information, manipulation of information and corruption of information [2]. There may be malfunctioning or malicious probes working in the system that manipulate the information to divert the traffic away to reduce the travel time of particular driver. Various entities can compromise data such as:

- Compromised vehicles: third parties or drivers could modify the hardware or software to report incorrect vehicle positions or speed readings. These modifications have occurred in European trucks' tachographs, which are supposed to record vehicles' driving times and speed to let authorities check adherence to mandatory driver rest periods [3].
- Impostor devices: a device spoofing other authorized devices. This compromise is of particular concern in the form of a Sybil attack [5] in which a device illegitimately claims multiple entities. Traffic-monitoring accu-

racy will degrade more if many vehicles simultaneously report incorrect information [3].

- Network intermediaries: intermediate device may able to modify the vehicle data during the transmission over wireless and wired communication [3].

3.3 Availability

Availability means accessibility and operation of ITS services by approved users. This handiness should not be halted by unauthorized users [1]. Many applications require soft or hard real time guarantees. However, meeting time deadlines make the application vulnerable to Denial of Service (DoS) attacks. The unreliable communication layer further intensifies the problem [4].

3.4 Accountability

ITS users should be accounted for all the changes to security parameters and applications that may intentionally or unintentionally harm the overall ITS system. These changes include updating, additions and deletions [1].

3.5 Authenticity

Authenticity prevents the illicit users from posing as legit users when communication with other ITS entities. ITS should not be managed and configured by any unauthorized user. Moreover, restricted services should be available to legitimate users [1]. Two way authentication is a possible security measure but is time consuming [2].

3.6 Privacy

ITS systems collect a lot of information about the users. This collected information should be processed in context of the operation of ITS system and applications hence protecting the fundamental rights and freedom of individuals. Moreover, the personal data should be protected against any kind of misuse [5]. One of the main challenges is data collection and its handling to fulfill requirements of application. There will always be a trade-off between privacy and application requirement. User acceptance is an important aspect

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of privacy. Sometimes the user has to choose between the safety application and data collected that violates his/her privacy. Privacy should be included from initial phases of development in any ITS (privacy by design) [2]. Another challenge is the fight against criminal acts and terrorism. Not only criminals and terrorists can be monitored using the ITS system but other users can also be monitored on individual levels by the operators and authorities having access rights to information [2]. Hence helpful in reconstruction of individual's route and deducing sensitive inferences. Various entities that can compromise privacy are listed below:

- Eavesdroppers: eavesdropper is an unauthorized third party that could monitor network transmissions for vehicle position readings and unique identifiers for tracking. In particular, third party could monitor wireless transmissions around sensitive locations to record which vehicles recurrently visit this area. Network identifiers, such as the International Mobile Subscriber Identifiers (IMSI) in the GSM (Global System for Mobile Communications) cell phone system, help to identify recurring visits. [3]
- Spyware: people that have access to on-board vehicle system could install software that directly reports vehicle positions to unauthorized network servers. [3]
- Insiders: most of privacy breaches occurs in critical systems are through insiders, during which insiders receives and stores reports from large numbers of different vehicles. Although access control mechanisms provide some protection, but several individuals, such as system administrators have root access to the system. [3]

3.7 Risk analysis and management

Risk analysis and management is the study of analyzing and managing the risk factors associated with the assets and possible attack in ITS nodes. Currently, solutions have been proposed but a proper working model is still missing [6].

3.8 Data-centric Trust and Verification

In ITS, data trustworthiness is more important than trustworthiness of ITS entities themselves. Hence vehicular applications need to ensure that the communicated information maintains its integrity. This can be achieved using public key cryptographic systems but then again an overhead (delay) is introduced which hinders fast processing of information especially for hard, real time applications [7].

3.9 Stakeholders Safety and Security Awareness

In any ITS system, safety and security is always focused on technology that implements it. The designers of system should also consider authority, operator and user awareness. This awareness not only includes the technical know-how for understanding and operating the system but also the access rights to the information contained by the system leading to administrative and political decisions. So, we can say that an ITS is highly a political matter and all the architectural authority issues should be discussed within political forums. Sadly, not only general public but politicians are also unaware of the sensitivity regarding this matter [2]. There is lack of literature on stakeholder safety and security awareness in ITS. Due to this there is a knowledge gap and it should be closed by educating the consumers. Privacy awareness is present in many other sectors like health but consumers are unaware of the privacy threats in ITS applications and services [2].

3.10 Low Tolerance for Errors

Security for many applications is based on probabilistic techniques. This creates a high margin for errors which is unacceptable for ITS applications. Given life or death nature of ITS applications, these errors should be reduced to a minimum (infinitesimally small). This can be achieved using deterministic approaches or probabilistic schemes with large enough security parameters. Security should focus on prevention of attacks rather than detection and recovery as detection alone will be insufficient for safety related applications [2].

3.11 Mobility & Volatility

Traditional ad hoc and sensor networks assume no or limited mobility. But in ITS system the users are highly mobile. Mobility is measured in miles per hour not meters. The brief interaction of communicating nodes in ITS restrict the use of reputation based approaches. Moreover, the short communication range between sender and receiver does not allow use of protocols that require significant interaction [4]. The node connectivity in ITS is highly momentary and perhaps a one time event. This implies vehicular networks do not need the long lived context and personal contact of devices. Hence, password secured channel establishment and gradual increase in the circle of trusted nodes may be impractical in ITS system [8].

3.12 Key Distribution

Key distribution is the main building block for security protocols. It involves significant challenges. Different manufacturers use different length and kinds of keys, so for proper communication between vehicles, coordination and interoperability between manufacturers will be required [4].

3.13 Delay-Sensitive Applications

Applications in ITS require minimal time for processing and overhead. Security mechanisms must take this into account and light weight protocols should be developed. These protocols should also be robust against DoS attacks. Hence a trade-off between robustness and cost due to tamper proof hardware should be achieved [8].

3.14 Heterogeneity

Taking into account the gradual deployment of ITS system, the varied technologies used in subsystems and their supported applications are also a challenge. The security solutions should retain flexibility for a range of applications with different requirements yet maintain their efficiency and interoperability [8].

3.15 Bootstrap

During initial phases of ITS deployment very few vehicles will be equipped with Dedicated Short Range Communications (DSRC) technology and infrastructure to support them will be little. Thus, during development of ITS applications we can assume that only a few nodes will be able to communicate successfully. The applications must be useful even under these limited conditions [4].

4 Attacks and Vulnerabilities

We cannot forestall every possible attack on ITS system but can enumerate a list of vulnerabilities and detected attacks on ITS.

4.1 Jamming/Denial of Service (DoS)

The attacker deliberately generates interfering transmissions that overwhelms and hence prevent communication within reception range. As the network coverage area can be well-defined, at least locally, jamming is a low-effort exploit opportunity. An attacker can relatively easily, without compromising cryptographic mechanisms and with limited transmission power, partition the vehicular network [8]. Not only does this render the application useless, it could increase the danger to the driver if he/she has depends on the application's information [8].

4.2 Fabrication Attacks

An adversary can initiate a fabrication attack by broadcasting false information into the network. An attacker may also choose to fabricate her own information, including her identity, location, or other application specific parameters. Defending against fabrication attacks in a vehicular network is particularly challenging, since the traditional remedy of using strong identities along with cryptographic authentication may conflict with the need to preserve the privacy of participants in the network. [4]

4.3 Alteration Attacks

A particularly insidious attack in a vehicular network is to alter existing data. This includes deliberately delaying the transmission of information, replaying earlier transmissions or altering the individual entries within a transmission. A malicious attacker might alter a message alerting vehicles to an obstacle ahead to persuade another vehicle that the lane is in fact clear. Clearly, applications on vehicular networks will need authentication of both the source of the data and the data itself. [5]

4.4 In-transit Traffic Tampering

Any node acting as a relay can disrupt communications of other nodes: it can drop or corrupt messages, or meaningfully modify messages. In this way, the reception of valuable or even critical traffic notifications or safety messages can be manipulated. Moreover, attackers can replay messages (e.g., to illegitimately obtain services such as traversing a toll check point). In fact,

tampering with in-transit messages may be simpler and more powerful than forgery attacks [8].

4.5 Impersonation

Message fabrication, alteration, and replay can also be used towards impersonation. Arguably, the source of messages, identified at each layer of the stack, may be of secondary importance. Often, it is not the source but the content (e.g., hazard warning) and the attributes of the message (freshness, locality, relevance to the receiver) that count the most [9].

4.6 Privacy Violation

With vehicular networks deployed, the collection of vehicle-specific information from overheard vehicular communications will become particularly easy. Then inferences on the drivers' personal data could be made, and thus violate her or his privacy. The vulnerability lies in the periodic and frequent vehicular network traffic: safety and traffic management messages, context-aware data access (e.g., maps, ferryboat schedules), transaction based communications (e.g., automated payments, car diagnostics), or other control messages (e.g., over-the-air registration with local highway authorities). In all such occasions, messages will include, by default, information (e.g., time, location, vehicle identifier, technical description, trip details) that could precisely identify the originating node (vehicle) as well as the drivers' actions and preferences [10].

4.7 On-board Tampering

Beyond abuse of the communication protocols, the attacker may select to tinker with data (e.g., velocity, location, status of vehicle parts) at their source, tampering with the on-board sensing and other hardware [9].

5 Discussion

Vehicles are getting safer, cleaner, and more intelligent. Information exchange among vehicles, and between vehicles and the roadside infrastructure is commonly regarded as a base technology to sustainably reduce road accidents and improve traffic efficiency. With ITS vision, vehicles are projected to be

fully connected using all their sensors and communication capabilities in the future. ITS do have a larger scope in the future, probably more in the developing countries than in the developed ones. Slowly but gradually all transport and rapid transit systems will continue to adopt a smarter way for ticketing and management of the systems so that the old technologies and mechanisms will slowly cease to exist. However, development of completely autonomous ITS systems, is a complex task requiring high economical resources and a large variety of technologies encompassing different research areas. Considering the billions of vehicles around the globe, ITS will have a gigantic network scale and managing it will be a challenge. Moreover, distribution of cryptographic keys by a large number of governing authorities will be quite an issue [11]. In order to develop the ITS system, one of the main issues are incentives. Vehicle manufacturers, consumers and the government would require incentives if ITS is successfully deployed. The interests of these three stakeholders is often conflicting and reconciling these interests is rather a difficult task [12].

For safety/security purpose, each vehicle is assumed to be equipped with a Dedicated Short-range Communication (DSRC) radio, a Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver, and onboard sensors. As vehicles are designed to broadcast messages about it status such as positions, speed etc., therefore, such system leads to cooperation between various communicating entities (i.e., Cooperative ITS). Cooperative communications is a promising technology for improving wireless communication performance through the use of transmission diversity offered by relay nodes [13]. It is especially interesting vehicular networks where system dynamics necessities the need for special logics to handle changing network configurations [14]. Cooperative ITS can greatly increase the quality and reliability of information available about the vehicles, their location and the road environment. Cooperative ITS improve existing and will lead to new services for the road users, which, in turn, will bring major social and economic benefits and lead to greater transport efficiency and increased safety. Due to the limited scope of existing risk analysis works, future efforts may focus on cooperative ITS [15] to be ensure effective connectivity among devices and systems.

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